

Afterword by the Artist

(On personal manner and individuality)

I studied painting from early youth — in art studios and a traditional academic art school for children. But even then I felt that this strict academic system was not for me. Classical still life, symmetry, the precise rendering of materials — glass, ceramics, or small objects — always seemed lifeless. The traditional approach with shadow, half-tone, and highlight never inspired me.

For many years I thought that I “couldn’t” show volume, that something was missing. Only later I understood — this is **my individuality**. I simply do not need to imitate reality. What interests me is **color, balance, and lightness of form**.

The only classical element I still use is **reflexes** — reflections of surrounding color that bring life to the surface. They help the painting breathe and connect one tone with another.

Now I understand that flatness and decorative rhythm are not limitations, but my own way of seeing. I don’t chase illusion — I create **a living surface of color** where everything is equal: line, tone, and space.

Keywords:

Decorative painting, color harmony, abstraction, composition, artistic education, freedom in art, individuality, Nona Dronova

